

KNOWLEDGE AND REPRESENTATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AMONG HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN MOROCCO

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Abstract

This study addresses a significant gap in the literature on environmental education, which has predominantly focused on Western contexts, by exploring the impact of demographic factors such as gender, educational level, and the presence of environmental clubs on students' participation in environmental activities in Moroccan cities. The research provides critical insights into the unique challenges faced by students in Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier, regions that have been underrepresented in existing studies. The findings reveal that while girls are more engaged in environmental discussions, overall participation in activities remains low across all groups. Despite students demonstrating a reasonable understanding of key environmental components and pollutants, there are significant areas where further educational interventions are needed. Correlation analysis indicates weak relationships between club membership and active participation in environmental activities, suggesting that a club alone does not ensure student engagement. However, a moderate correlation between club involvement and discussions on environmental issues highlights the potential of these clubs to raise awareness. The weak link between discussions and specific pollutant knowledge suggests that these conversations overlook essential environmental topics. These findings underscore the need to strengthen environmental clubs, diversify activities, and promote deeper, more comprehensive discussions to enhance student engagement and awareness. This study contributes to the broader field by providing actionable recommendations for fostering more effective environmental education in non-Western contexts.

Keywords: Environmental Education, Environmental Clubs, Pollutant Knowledge, Morocco.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental education is essential for equipping younger generations to tackle the escalating ecological challenges of our time. By fostering awareness and encouraging pro-environmental behaviors, educational programs play a crucial role in shaping the future stewards of the planet [1, 2].

The goal of environmental education is to develop a deep understanding of ecological issues among students and motivate them to take concrete actions to protect the environment [3]. However, despite extensive research on environmental education in Western contexts, there remains a significant gap in understanding its effectiveness in different cultural settings, such as Morocco [4, 5].

This study aims to fill this gap by examining the factors that influence student engagement, awareness, and participation in environmental activities in the Moroccan cities of Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. Previous research has shown that cultural and social contexts play a crucial role in how students perceive and participate in environmental initiatives [6, 7]. By exploring these dynamics in a non-Western context, this research provides valuable insights into the existing literature and offers perspectives for developing more effective and locally adapted educational programs.

This research focuses on key demographic and educational factors, including gender, grade level, and the presence of environmental clubs in schools, to assess their impact on students' involvement in environmental initiatives. Prior studies suggest that gender plays a significant role in environmental engagement, with girls often demonstrating greater concern for ecological issues than boys [8,9].

This gender difference could be linked to cultural and social factors that influence students' attitudes and behaviors toward the environment [10]. Additionally, the availability of environmental clubs has been associated with higher levels of student participation in environmental activities, suggesting that these clubs can serve as important platforms for environmental education and engagement [11, 12].

The study further investigates the practical aspects of student engagement, such as club membership, participation in activities inside and outside school, and the frequency of discussions about environmental issues.

Understanding these dynamics is critical for identifying the factors that encourage or hinder active involvement in ecological initiatives. For example, frequent discussions on environmental issues can foster increased awareness and a better understanding of ecological problems among students [13, 14].

Moreover, this research assesses students' knowledge of key environmental components and pollutants, which are important indicators of environmental literacy [15, 3]. Adequate environmental literacy is essential for enabling students to understand the interconnections between human actions and environmental impacts and encourage them to adopt sustainable behaviors [16, 17].

In conclusion, this study not only contributes to a better understanding of environmental education in a Moroccan context but also offers practical recommendations for enhancing student engagement and promoting a culture of sustainability. By integrating diverse and context-specific educational approaches, educators and policymakers can improve the effectiveness of environmental education programs and prepare a new generation of proactive and environmentally conscious citizens [18, 19].

Research Questions

This study aims to explore the following research questions:

1. How does gender distribution influence participation and awareness in environmental activities among high school students in Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier?
2. What is the impact of grade level and the presence of environmental clubs on student engagement in ecological activities?
3. How frequently and in what contexts do students discuss environmental issues, and what factors drive these conversations?
4. What level of knowledge do students have about the main components of the environment and key pollutants affecting water, air, and soil quality?
5. What correlations exist between demographic factors, club membership, and participation in environmental activities, and how do these factors drive or hinder student engagement?

By addressing these questions, this study aims to provide actionable insights for tailoring environmental education to maximize student engagement and awareness, ultimately fostering a generation of environmentally conscious and proactive individuals.

2. METHODS

This study was conducted with a sample of 433 secondary school students from the Moroccan cities of Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. The primary goal was to explore students' involvement in environmental activities and assess their knowledge of environmental components and pollutants.

2.1 Sample Description

The study sample consists of 433 high school students from the Moroccan cities of Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier, with the distribution as follows: Fez contributes 130 students, representing 30% of the total sample; Sefrou provides 96 students, accounting for 22% of the sample; and Tangier, the largest contributor, includes 207 students, making up 48% of the sample. The participants vary in gender and grade level, with a majority of girls in each city and representation from both the first and second years of high school. The sample size was determined through a power analysis, which established that 433 participants would be sufficient to detect medium effect sizes with an 80% power at a 5% significance level. The focus on urban areas implies that the findings are most applicable to similar urban contexts within Morocco, offering insights that are particularly relevant to the environmental education landscape in these settings.

2.2 Data Collection Tools

The main data collection tool was a structured questionnaire designed to gather information on students' environmental activities and their knowledge of environmental components and pollutants. The questionnaire comprised several sections:

1. Student Introduction and Environmental Activities: This section collected basic demographic information (e.g., gender, grade level) and details about students' involvement in environmental activities, including:
 - Presence and membership in an environmental club.
 - Participation in environmental activities within and outside the school.
 - Frequency of discussions about environmental issues with peers and family.
2. General Environmental Questions: This section assessed students' knowledge of environmental components and pollutants, including:
 - Identification of the main components of the environment.
 - Recognition of different types of pollutants affecting water, air, and soil.

2.3 Development of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire was developed following a review of existing literature on environmental education and student engagement [11, 15]. The design aimed to be both comprehensive and straightforward, ensuring that students could easily understand and respond to the questions. The questionnaire captured both qualitative and quantitative aspects of students' environmental knowledge and activities.

2.4 Pilot Testing

Before the main data collection, the questionnaire was pilot-tested with a small group of students to identify potential issues with question clarity or interpretation. Feedback from the pilot test informed refinements to the questionnaire, ensuring clarity and effectiveness in data collection.

2.5 Data Collection Procedure

Data collection followed these steps:

1. Authorization: Permission was obtained from school administrations to conduct the study and distribute the questionnaires.
2. Consent: Informed consent was obtained from all students, who were briefed on the study's purpose, the confidentiality of their responses, and their right to withdraw at any time [20].
3. Questionnaire Distribution and Collection: Trained surveyors distributed and collected the questionnaires in person at the schools. They provided instructions and assistance as needed, ensuring a uniform administration process across all participating schools.

2.6 Data Coding and Entry

After collection, the questionnaires were reviewed for completeness and accuracy. Responses were then coded and entered into a statistical software program (SPSS or R) for analysis. Data entry was meticulously conducted to ensure accuracy and reliability.

2.7 Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using statistical software, with the following steps:

1. **Descriptive Statistics:** Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, providing an overview of response distributions by city, gender, and grade level.
2. **Correlation Analyses:** The Spearman correlation coefficient was used to examine relationships between variables such as gender, club membership, activity participation, discussion frequency, and pollutant knowledge. Spearman's rank correlation was chosen due to its suitability for ordinal data and its ability to assess monotonic relationships without assuming linearity [21].
3. **Handling of Missing Data:** Missing data were addressed using pairwise deletion, as the missing values were minimal and did not significantly affect the results. For instances with more substantial missing data, sensitivity analyses were conducted to ensure the robustness of the findings.
4. **Comparisons between Cities:** Comparative analyses were conducted to identify differences and similarities in student environmental involvement and awareness across the cities. This included examining how contextual factors in each city might influence students' engagement and knowledge.

2.8 Statistical Tools

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS and R, which are widely used in educational research for their robust capabilities in handling complex data. These tools enabled detailed analysis, providing insights into the factors influencing students' environmental education and engagement.

2.9 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were prioritized throughout the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing the data. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without any negative consequences [20].

3. RESULTS

3.1 Student Introduction and Environmental Activities:

The results presented below are based on 433 questionnaires that were completed and collected from secondary school students.

Figure 1: Breakdown by gender of the students surveyed in the two years of the baccalaureate in the cities of Tangier, Fez and Sefrou

Figure 1 above displays the gender distribution of students involved in environmental activities across the cities of Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. In Fez, the majority of students participating in environmental activities are female, representing 63.85% of the participants, while males constitute 36.15%. This significant gender disparity suggests that environmental programs in Fez might be more appealing or accessible to female students. Similarly, Sefrou shows a higher participation rate of females at 61.46%, with males making up 38.54% of the participants. Although the difference is slightly less pronounced than in Fez, it still indicates a strong female predominance. Tangier has the most balanced gender distribution among the three cities, with 59.42% females and 40.58% males. Despite being the most balanced, females still represent a larger proportion of the participants.

3.1.1 Participation in environmental clubs and activities

Figure 2: Distribution of responses from students in the first and second year of the baccalaureate concerning the presence of environmental clubs in their establishment in Tangier, Fez, and Sefrou

Figure 2, shows the presence of environmental clubs varies significantly across Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. In Fez, only 47.69% of schools have environmental clubs, leaving 52.31% without, indicating a limited infrastructure for environmental education. This significant gap highlights the need for more organized environmental activities to enhance student engagement and awareness. The lack of clubs in over half of the schools suggests that many students in Fez may not have sufficient opportunities to participate in structured environmental education programs.

In contrast, Sefrou shows a higher presence of environmental clubs, with 62.50% of schools having these clubs, reflecting a robust infrastructure and prioritization of environmental education. This high presence likely contributes to higher levels of awareness and engagement among students. Tangier follows closely with 59.42% of schools hosting environmental clubs, although 40.58% still lack these clubs, indicating room for improvement. The higher percentages in Sefrou and Tangier suggest that these cities have more developed strategies and resources for promoting environmental education compared to Fez. To enhance environmental awareness and participation, Fez needs increased investment in establishing clubs, Sefrou should continue its effective strategies, and Tangier should focus on expanding club access to all schools, ensuring comprehensive environmental education across the city.

Figure 3: Distribution of responses from students in the first and second year of the baccalaureate concerning the presence of environmental clubs in their establishment in Tangier, Fez, and Sefrou

Figure 3, illustrates significant differences in membership rates in environmental clubs among students in Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. In Fez, only 12.31% of students are members of environmental clubs, while a substantial 87.69% are not, indicating a very low level of engagement. This low membership rate suggests potential barriers to joining clubs, such as lack of awareness, insufficient promotion of club benefits, or unappealing club activities. These barriers need to be addressed to foster greater student participation.

In Sefrou, 22.92% of students are members of environmental clubs, with 77.08% not participating. Although this membership rate is higher than in Fez, it still indicates that a significant majority of students are not engaged in these clubs. The higher membership

rate compared to Fez suggests that Sefrou's strategies to promote club membership are somewhat more effective but still require enhancement to reach a larger portion of the student population.

Tangier shows a membership rate of 15.94%, with 84.06% of students not being members of environmental clubs. While this rate is better than Fez's, it is still lower than Sefrou's, indicating moderate engagement levels. The relatively low membership across all three cities points to the need for improved strategies to make environmental clubs more attractive and accessible to students. Efforts should include better promotion of the clubs, showcasing the benefits of membership, and ensuring that club activities are engaging and relevant to students' interests. By addressing these issues, schools in Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier can enhance student involvement in environmental education and activities.

The third chart shows the participation rates in environmental activities among students in Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. In Fez, 24.62% of students participate in environmental activities, while a significant 75.38% do not. This low participation rate suggests that environmental activities may not be sufficiently engaging or accessible to the majority of students. Potential barriers such as lack of awareness, insufficient promotion, or logistical issues might be preventing greater student involvement.

In Sefrou, the participation rate is slightly higher, with 27.08% of students engaging in environmental activities and 72.92% not participating. Although this is an improvement over Fez, the fact that nearly three-quarters of the students are not involved indicates that there are still considerable obstacles to participation. The higher participation rate in Sefrou suggests that some strategies might be more effective, but there is still a need for further improvements to engage more students.

Figure 4: Participation in environmental activities, within or outside the establishment, based on students' responses in the first and second years in a baccalaureate in Tangier, Fez, and Sefrou

Tangier shows the lowest participation rate, with only 23.19% of students involved in environmental activities and a substantial 76.81% not participating. Despite having a

relatively strong presence of environmental clubs, this low participation rate highlights a disconnect between the availability of clubs and active student engagement. It suggests that simply having clubs is not enough; the activities offered must be appealing, accessible, and well-promoted to encourage student participation.

3.1.2 Frequency of Environmental Discussions

Figure Evocation of the environment with their entourage according to the responses from the students in the first and the second years of the baccalaureate in Tangier, Fez, and Sefrou. The survey was conducted among 433 students.

Figure 5: Distribution of the frequency of discussions about the environment according to the responses of Students in the first and the second years of the baccalaureate in Tangier, Fez, and Sefrou

In Fez, 13.08% of students discuss environmental issues often, 76.15% sometimes, and 10.77% never. This suggests that while a majority of students engage in conversations about the environment occasionally, a smaller proportion discusses these issues frequently, and a notable segment never discusses them at all. The relatively high percentage of occasional discussions indicates a moderate level of environmental awareness, though there is room for increasing the frequency of these discussions to deepen students' engagement.

In Sefrou, the frequency of discussions is somewhat similar, with 19.79% of students discussing environmental issues often, 73.96% sometimes, and 6.25% never. The higher percentage of students who frequently discuss environmental issues compared to Fez suggests a slightly more engaged student population. The lower percentage of students who never discuss these issues indicates better overall awareness and willingness to engage in environmental topics.

In Tangier, 9.18% of students discuss environmental issues often, 87.44% sometimes, and 3.38% never. While Tangier shows the highest percentage of students who sometimes discuss environmental issues, it has the lowest percentage of frequent discussants. This suggests that while environmental topics are moderately present in

discussions, they are not deeply ingrained in the students' everyday conversations, pointing to a need for strategies to encourage more frequent and in-depth discussions.

3.2 knowledge of environmental components and pollutants, including:

The students were asked to list three types of pollutants of human or natural origin in their region (city) that degrade water quality. Name three types of pollutants of human or natural origin in your region (city) that degrade water quality), the analysis takes on a different perspective:

Figure 6: Distribution of the main water pollutants by city according to the responses of Students in the first and the second years of the baccalaureate in Tangier, Fez, and Sefrou

The analysis reveals that Tangier residents perceive general waste (157 mentions) as the most significant pollutant degrading water quality, followed by Fes (113) and Sefrou (83), indicating a widespread recognition of this issue across all three cities. Furthermore, industrial waste is particularly identified as a major water pollutant in Tangier (46), likely due to the city's more intense industrial activities, while Fes (16) and Sefrou (10) have fewer mentions, possibly reflecting less industrialization or lower public awareness. Additionally, wastewater is notably perceived as a significant pollutant in Tangier (62), suggesting heightened awareness of the impact of untreated or poorly managed wastewater, whereas Fes (8) and Sefrou (9) report lower concern. Lastly, the "Other" pollutants category, with Tangier (29) again leading, indicates a recognition of a broader range of pollutants, such as agricultural runoff or chemical spills, compared to Sefrou (8) and Fes (6). This comprehensive view underscores the varying levels of environmental awareness and pollution challenges in these cities.

The interpretation suggests that the varying levels of concern about water pollutants across Fes, Sefrou, and Tangier reflect the unique environmental challenges each city faces. Tangier's higher response numbers across all categories indicate a heightened awareness among its residents, likely due to factors such as a larger population, more extensive industrial activities, and perhaps more visible pollution problems. In contrast, Fes and Sefrou, while still recognizing the importance of water pollutants, report fewer

concerns, which may be due to smaller populations, lower levels of industrialization, or more effective water management systems already in place.

In conclusion, this figure underscores the public perception of water pollution in these regions, with Tangier's residents demonstrating the greatest concern. This disparity suggests that Tangier might benefit from targeted environmental education and enhanced pollution control initiatives to address these issues effectively.

Figure 7: Distribution of the main air pollutants by item and by city according to the responses of Students in the first and the second years of the baccalaureate questioned in Tangier, Fez, and Sefrou

The figure reveals that Tangier leads in reported car emissions, with 134 responses, indicating that residents view vehicle exhaust as a significant environmental pollutant, while Fez follows with 88 mentions and Sefrou records the lowest at 60, possibly reflecting less traffic or fewer concerns in these smaller, less industrialized cities. Similarly, industrial emissions are most significant in Tangier, with 194 responses, highlighting the city's industrial activities and their environmental impact; Fez also shows substantial concern with 107 responses, whereas Sefrou reports fewer concerns at 83, likely due to its smaller industrial base. Furthermore, the "Others" category, though smaller in quantity, mirrors this trend, with Tangier slightly ahead at 9 responses compared to Fez and Sefrou, each with 7, suggesting that Tangier's residents are more aware of a broader range of environmental pollutants beyond car and industrial emissions.

The interpretation indicates that residents of Tangier are more concerned about pollution from cars and industrial activities than those in Fez and Sefrou, likely due to Tangier's larger size, higher traffic density, and more extensive industrial operations, which contribute to more visible and impactful pollution problems. The significant difference in industrial emissions between Tangier and the other two cities underscores Tangier's role as a major industrial hub in the region, bringing with it corresponding environmental challenges. In contrast, while Fez shows notable concern about both industrial emissions and car pollution, it reports fewer issues compared to Tangier, likely reflecting its slightly

smaller population and industrial base. Nevertheless, the pollution concerns in Fez remain significant and warrant attention. Sefrou, with the lowest numbers across all categories, likely benefits from being a smaller, less industrialized city, which may explain the lower perception of pollution-related issues. However, the existing concerns, particularly regarding car and industrial emissions, demonstrate that even smaller cities are not immune to environmental pollution.

In conclusion, the data suggests that Tangier, as a larger and more industrially active city, faces more significant pollution challenges, especially from cars and industrial activities, compared to Fez and Sefrou. These findings emphasize the need for targeted environmental policies and pollution control measures in Tangier, while also addressing pollution concerns in Fez and Sefrou to ensure sustainable urban development across all three cities.

Figure 8: Distribution of the main soil pollutants by item and by city according to the responses of Students in the first and the second years of the baccalaureate in Tangier, Fez, and Sefrou

The figure illustrates the comparative quantities of household waste, chemical fertilizers, and other pollutants across the cities of Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. Tangier stands out with the highest levels of all three pollutant types, particularly household waste at 144 units, followed by Fez with 91 units and Sefrou with 75 units. This trend suggests that Tangier, as the largest city among the three, generates the most waste, likely due to its higher population density and urban activities. Similarly, Tangier also leads in the use of chemical fertilizers, with 53 units compared to Fez's 23 and Sefrou's 14, indicating more extensive agricultural or landscaping activities in Tangier. The "Others" category follows the same pattern, with Tangier reporting 73 units, significantly more than Fez's and Sefrou's 23 and 15 units, respectively.

These findings highlight the environmental challenges faced by Tangier as a rapidly growing urban center, with higher waste production and chemical usage contributing to potential environmental degradation. Fez, while showing moderate levels of pollutants, still faces notable environmental concerns, particularly regarding household waste and

chemical fertilizers. Sefrou, as the smallest city, reports the lowest levels of pollutants across all categories, reflecting its smaller scale and possibly more controlled waste and chemical management practices. Overall, the data emphasizes the need for targeted waste management and pollution control strategies in Tangier, while also addressing the environmental issues in Fez and Sefrou to ensure sustainable development across all three cities.

In conclusion, the data reveals significant disparities in waste production and chemical usage across the three cities, with Tangier facing the most pronounced environmental challenges due to its larger size and more intensive urban and agricultural activities. Fez and Sefrou, though generating lower levels of pollutants, still show considerable concern, particularly in managing household waste and chemical fertilizers. These findings underscore the necessity for robust and tailored environmental policies in Tangier to mitigate its higher pollution levels, while also ensuring that Fez and Sefrou implement effective measures to address their specific environmental issues. By doing so, all three cities can work towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly urban development.

3.3 Correlation Analysis of Student Environmental Engagement and Knowledge

Figure 9: Spearman correlation matrix of student engagement, environmental knowledge, and club participation variables in Moroccan high schools

The Spearman correlation matrix reveals the relationships between various variables related to student engagement, environmental knowledge, and participation in environmental club activities in Moroccan high schools. Below is a refined interpretation of each pair of variables, along with actionable recommendations for improving environmental education practices.

3.3.1 Environment Club and Club Member

The very weak positive correlation (0.08) between being part of an environment club and being a club member, in general, suggests that while there is a slight tendency for students involved in any club to also join an environment club, the relationship is not strong. This indicates that students who are interested in the environment may have unique motivations compared to those joining other clubs. To capitalize on this, environmental clubs could tailor their outreach and activities to appeal specifically to students with an interest in environmental issues, perhaps by highlighting unique environmental challenges and opportunities for advocacy.

3.3.2 Club Member and Participates in Activities

The moderate positive correlation (0.48) between being a club member and participating in club activities indicates that club members are somewhat likely to engage in the activities organized by the club. This finding suggests that clubs are effective in engaging their members, but there is room for improvement. Schools could boost participation further by promoting the benefits of active involvement and showcasing successful environmental projects or initiatives undertaken by the clubs. By doing so, they might indirectly increase environmental awareness and education.

3.3.3 Participates in Activities and Talks about Environment

The very weak negative correlation (-0.07) between participation in activities and talking about the environment suggests that participation in club activities does not necessarily translate into more conversations about environmental issues. This could imply that the activities are not focused on fostering discussions or that students do not continue these conversations outside of club activities. To address this, clubs could integrate more discussion-based components into their activities, such as debates or group reflections on environmental issues, to encourage continued dialogue beyond the club setting.

3.3.4 Talks about Environment and Water Pollutants

The weak negative correlation (-0.09) between talking about the environment and awareness of water pollutants suggests that those who frequently talk about environmental issues might have slightly less awareness of specific pollutants. This finding points to a need for integrating more detailed information about pollutants, such as water pollution, into environmental discussions. Ensuring that conversations cover a broad range of topics, including specific pollutants, could enhance overall awareness and understanding.

3.3.5 Water Pollutants and Air Pollutants

The weak negative correlation (-0.19) between awareness of water and air pollutants suggests a slight inverse relationship. This could mean that individuals who are more aware of one type of pollutant might be less aware of another. Educational programs should ensure a balanced approach to teaching about different types of pollutants. Integrating comprehensive modules on both air and water pollution in environmental education can help provide students with a well-rounded understanding of these critical issues.

3.3.6 Air Pollutants and Soil Pollutants

The weak positive correlation (0.13) between awareness of air and soil pollutants suggests some overlap in awareness of different types of pollution. This indicates that individuals who are aware of air pollutants are somewhat likely to also be aware of soil pollutants. Educational initiatives that simultaneously address multiple types of pollutants could leverage this relationship to improve overall environmental awareness, perhaps through interdisciplinary projects that highlight the interconnectedness of various environmental issues.

3.3.7 Environment Club and Talks about Environment

The weak negative correlation (-0.21) between being part of an environment club and discussing environmental issues indicates that members might talk slightly less about the environment compared to non-members. This counterintuitive finding could suggest that environment club members feel that their club participation is sufficient or that clubs need to foster more external communication about environmental topics. Clubs might consider encouraging members to initiate discussions outside of club meetings or engage in community outreach to broaden awareness and advocacy efforts.

3.3.8 Overall Implications and Recommendations

The generally weak correlations observed in this study suggest that the relationships between the variables are not straightforward and may be influenced by other, unmeasured factors. The findings indicate that environmental education could benefit from several enhancements:

Diverse and Integrated Curriculum: Schools should aim for a well-rounded curriculum that covers all aspects of environmental science, including both major and minor pollutants (Monroe and Adams, 2018). This approach can address gaps in knowledge and provide students with a more comprehensive understanding of environmental issues.

Interactive and Engaging Learning Methods: Incorporating interactive and discussion-based learning methods can significantly enhance student engagement and knowledge retention (Fielding and Head, 2012). Schools should consider integrating more hands-on activities, debates, and collaborative projects that allow students to explore environmental issues in depth.

Continuous Program Improvement: Regularly reviewing and adapting the curriculum to address imbalances and ensure comprehensive coverage of all relevant topics is

crucial. Schools should assess the effectiveness of their programs periodically and make necessary adjustments to maintain high-quality environmental education that meets the needs of diverse student populations.

In conclusion, the Spearman correlation matrix provides valuable insights into the interrelationships between various factors in environmental education. The findings underscore the need for a balanced and comprehensive curriculum that equally addresses different types of pollutants and incorporates interactive, engaging learning methods. By continuously reviewing and adapting their programs, schools can enhance students' environmental knowledge and better prepare them to address diverse environmental challenges effectively. Additionally, fostering a culture of open discussion both within and beyond the classroom can help build a more environmentally aware and proactive student body.

4. DISCUSSION

The results of this study reveal significant disparities in student engagement with environmental education across the cities of Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. These differences are influenced by several factors, including the presence of environmental clubs, gender, and levels of knowledge about pollutants. Understanding these disparities is crucial for developing targeted educational strategies to enhance student engagement and awareness in diverse contexts.

4.1 Gender Differences and Participation in Environmental Activities

The findings indicate that girls show higher participation in environmental discussions across all the cities studied. This observation aligns with prior research [8, 9], which found that girls often exhibit greater ecological awareness and a stronger inclination to engage in environmental activities. One possible explanation is that societal and cultural norms may encourage girls more than boys to express concern for communal and ecological well-being. However, despite this trend, the overall active participation in environmental activities remains low for both genders. This underlines the necessity for more inclusive and varied approaches to boost broader participation. For instance, incorporating male role models in environmental education programs and designing activities that specifically appeal to boys, such as competitive or outdoor adventure-based learning, could help bridge this gap [25]. Moreover, research by Gilligan et al. [26] suggests that mixed-gender teams in environmental projects can foster mutual learning and increase engagement among both boys and girls by promoting collaboration and shared responsibility.

4.2 Role of Environmental Clubs and School Infrastructure

The presence of environmental clubs in schools varies significantly between cities, directly impacting student engagement levels. Sefrou, with 62.5% of schools hosting environmental clubs, exemplifies a successful model of environmental education infrastructure. However, the mere presence of these clubs does not guarantee active participation. The low engagement rates observed suggest that environmental clubs need to evolve beyond mere awareness-raising and incorporate more interactive and hands-

on activities to capture students' interest. This is supported by [11], who highlights the importance of engaging, experiential learning opportunities. Furthermore, recent studies by [22] and [25] indicate that activities that are locally relevant and directly connected to students' everyday experiences are more effective in sustaining their interest and commitment. Clubs could integrate project-based learning approaches, where students work on real-life environmental problems within their communities, thus enhancing both engagement and learning outcomes.

4.3 Frequency of Discussions on Environmental Issues

Frequent discussions about environmental issues are critical for enhancing student engagement and fostering a deeper understanding of ecological challenges. The study's data shows that while occasional discussions about environmental issues are common, frequent and sustained discussions are less prevalent, particularly in Tangier. This finding emphasizes the need for educational strategies that encourage regular, in-depth conversations about environmental topics. Integrating environmental education across various subjects and organizing discussion-based activities, such as debates, panels, and environmental storytelling, can foster deeper engagement, as suggested by [28]. Additionally, [29] highlights the effectiveness of peer-led discussions and student forums in encouraging more frequent and meaningful dialogue among students. Such forums provide a platform for students to voice their concerns, share knowledge, and collaboratively explore solutions to environmental problems, thereby promoting a more active and participatory learning environment.

4.4 Awareness of Pollutants and Environmental Education

Knowledge about pollutants (water, air, and soil) varies significantly between cities, reflecting the unique environmental challenges faced by each region. Tangier, a larger and more industrialized urban center, demonstrates greater awareness of pollution issues compared to Fez and Sefrou, which are less industrialized. This variation in awareness underscores the need for educational programs to adopt a balanced and holistic approach to teaching different types of pollutants, as emphasized by [15]. Incorporating knowledge about air and water pollutants into environmental education could provide students with a more comprehensive understanding of these critical issues. Research by [21] supports this view, suggesting that interdisciplinary approaches, which combine scientific knowledge with social and ethical perspectives, can enhance students' understanding and foster more environmentally responsible behaviors. Additionally, recent findings by [30] recommend using digital tools and simulations to teach about pollution and its impacts, offering an immersive and interactive learning experience that can improve retention and comprehension.

4.5 Correlations and the Complexity of Environmental Behaviors

The correlation analysis reveals generally weak relationships between the studied variables, suggesting that other factors, not included in this analysis, may influence environmental behaviors and awareness. This complexity points to the multifaceted nature of environmental engagement, where factors such as socio-economic

background, parental influence, and personal values may play a significant role [31]. The findings indicate that participation in clubs does not necessarily lead to increased discussions about environmental issues, suggesting that club activities may not always prioritize dialogue, or that students do not continue these conversations outside of club settings. To improve the effectiveness of environmental clubs, it would be beneficial to integrate diverse environmental topics into club activities and encourage discussions about environmental issues both within and outside the club environment [20, 23, 32] further propose the inclusion of community-based projects and partnerships with local environmental organizations to provide students with practical experiences and enhance their commitment to environmental stewardship.

4.6 Suggestions for Future Research

To build upon these findings, future studies could explore the impact of additional demographic factors, such as socio-economic status, ethnicity, and access to environmental resources, on environmental awareness and engagement. Moreover, longitudinal studies could observe how environmental attitudes and behaviors evolve, providing insights into the long-term impact of educational interventions. Future research should also evaluate the effectiveness of specific educational interventions, such as awareness programs, service-learning projects, and digital platforms, to identify the most effective approaches [33]. Additionally, considering the influence of social media and technology on environmental awareness among youth could provide valuable insights, as suggested by [34].

Finally, this study highlights the importance of diversifying educational approaches to enhance student engagement in environmental education. By improving the visibility and attractiveness of environmental clubs, diversifying the activities offered, and fostering more in-depth discussions on environmental topics, schools can significantly increase student awareness and engagement. These efforts will not only enhance environmental education but also prepare students to become proactive and informed citizens capable of addressing future environmental challenges. To achieve this, educators and policymakers must consider integrating new pedagogical strategies, including experiential learning, community engagement, and the use of technology, to create a dynamic and inclusive learning environment.

5. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the critical role of environmental education in fostering ecological awareness among high school students in non-Western contexts, specifically in the Moroccan cities of Fez, Sefrou, and Tangier. The research highlights significant disparities in student engagement, influenced by factors such as gender, the presence of environmental clubs, and regional differences in environmental awareness and knowledge. The findings suggest that while environmental clubs have the potential to enhance awareness, their mere presence is insufficient to ensure active student participation. Instead, a more comprehensive approach is needed—one that integrates

diverse, interactive, and locally relevant activities that resonate with students' interests and experiences.

Furthermore, the study reveals a gap in how environmental topics are discussed and understood, particularly regarding specific pollutants and their impacts. This indicates a need for educational strategies that promote frequent and meaningful discussions on a broad range of environmental issues, both within and outside the classroom. The correlations observed also suggest that environmental behaviors and awareness are influenced by a complex interplay of factors, requiring a multifaceted educational approach.

To enhance the effectiveness of environmental education, it is crucial to diversify club activities, foster a school culture that encourages open dialogue on environmental topics, and leverage innovative educational methods that engage students more deeply. Additionally, addressing logistical barriers and promoting inclusivity in environmental programs can help bridge the engagement gap and ensure that all students, regardless of background or gender, are actively involved in environmental initiatives.

Looking ahead, future research should explore the broader socio-cultural and economic factors that influence environmental engagement and consider longitudinal studies to better understand the evolution of environmental attitudes over time. By doing so, educators and policymakers can develop targeted interventions that effectively address the specific needs of diverse student populations.

Ultimately, this study contributes to the broader field of environmental education by offering actionable insights for fostering more effective educational practices in non-Western contexts. By equipping young people with the knowledge and skills to engage with environmental challenges critically, we can prepare a new generation of environmentally conscious and proactive citizens who are ready to advocate for and implement sustainable solutions in their communities. This comprehensive approach to environmental education is not just an academic imperative but a vital strategy for global ecological sustainability.

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